

BUTTERFLIES

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Abstract:- Butterflies are a very beautiful and fantasy creature on Earth. 'September' is a month of butterflies in India, because a large number of different butterflies we can be captured in this month all over the country. I searched some butterflies of my college campus, and I started researched on these, to get some knowledge about this beautiful creature. I write about its origin, larvae, life cycle; in a systematic order. The conclusion is to get some facts and points about the butterflies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Butterflies are the most familiar of insects to humans. Here according to data, there are 17,500 species of butterflies in the world, in India there are 1,500 species of butterflies. The largest butterfly in the world is Ornithoptera alexandrae (Queen Alexandra's birdwing), whereas in India the largest is Himalayan butterfly 'Golden Birdwing' (Troides aeacus) the female birdwing has wingspan 194mm; in male it is 190mm.

Fig 1 Golden Birdwing (Troides aeacus).

Fig 2 (Queen Alexandra's Birdwing) Ornithoptera alexandrae.

➤ Background

- *How can butterflies get to know the nectar?*

The butterfly can see the UV light spectrum and the flowers that reflect UV light to guide the butterfly to the nectar. Butterflies can also detect nectars or pollens from a particular plant through colours and smells. Butterflies are good pollinators and they have sucking receptors on their feet.

II. METHODOLOGY

Fig 3 Pachliopta aristolochiae.
Scientific Name: Pachliopta aristolochiae. (Common Rose.)

➤ Classification:

Phylum: Arthropoda.

Class: Insecta.

Order: Lepidoptera.

Family: Papilionoidea.

Genus: Pachliopta.

- **Origin:** The origin of this butterfly is unknown. The Greek word ‘aristolochiae’ means “Birth worth.”
- **Larvae:** The larvae of this butterfly feed on a variety of plants such as Aristolochic, Apama, Thottea.
- **Wingspan:** 3-3.5 inches (75-85mm).

➤ **Life Cycle:**

• **Eggs:**

The female selecting a healthy host plant to lay her round and reddish-brown eggs with fine black markings. The eggs are placed on the top, underside of leaves or even on shoots.

• **Caterpillar:**

The caterpillar is a velvety- maroon colour. It is bulky and slow in its movement. The caterpillars feed on the host plants until they form their chrysalis.

Fig 4 Caterpillar of Pachliopta.

• **Pupa:**

The pupa is brownish with various shades of brown and pink markings. The distinguishable feature of the common rose pupa is the presence of large semi-circular projections on the back of the abdomen, thorax and head.

Fig 5 Pupa of Pachliopta.

Fig 6 Aphrissa statira.
Scientific Name: Aphrissa statira.

➤ **Classification:**

Phylum: Arthropoda.

Class: Insecta.

Order: Lepidoptera.

Family: Pieridae.

Genus: Aphrissa.

- **Origin:** These butterflies are also called ‘Statira Sulphur.’ Medium-sized yellow butterflies. Females are paler than males.
- **Wingspan:** 2.37 inches (6cm) to 3.12 inches (7.9cm).

➤ **Lifecycle-**

• **Oviposition:**

Female statira sulfur lay their eggs on young leaves of host plant. These are usually two or three broods per year.

• **Caterpillar:**

These butterflies have two forms of caterpillars, that is a reason it has two different subspecies. The larvae which feed on Leguminosae are orange or green with a dark blue band and an orange head. The larvae form which feeds on Bignoniaceae is pale green with a yellow longitudinal stripe and a dark green head.

• **Pupa:**

The pupa of these butterflies turns grey to pale blue- green chrysalis.

III. CONCLUSION

Through this research, I analyzed that every butterfly has a different characteristic feature. The life cycle of butterflies is beautiful. It first begins with eggs, it turns into larvae(caterpillar) then pupa at last, it turns into a butterfly.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. en.wikipedia.org
- [2]. www.coursehero.com
- [3]. www.iro.umontreal.ca
- [4]. www.jungledragon.com
- [5]. nhpbs.org
- [6]. www.gbif.org
- [7]. With the help of teachers.
- [8]. With the help of www.ijisrt website.
- [9]. With the help of research papers.